

Diagnostic Role of Fiberoptic Bronchoscopy in the Management of Lung Collapse

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Abstract:

Introduction: Flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy has become an essential procedure for diagnosing and managing various respiratory conditions. Persistent lung collapse or collapse of small air sacs in the lungs is sometimes evaluated using bronchoscopy. The cause may be a blockage from thick mucous, a foreign body, or a tumor. Many diagnostic procedures can be performed using flexible bronchoscopy such as bronchial washings, bronchoalveolar lavage, bronchial brushings, endobronchial biopsy, transbronchial lung biopsy, and transbronchial needle aspiration. The role of flexible bronchoscopy in the therapeutic and diagnostic management of lung collapse is still under scientific evaluation.

Aim: To study the role of flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy in the therapeutic and diagnostic management of lung collapse.

Materials and Methods: A hospital-based retrospective observational study was done on 36 patients who were admitted with lung collapse at Government Hospital for chest and communicable diseases, Visakhapatnam. Patients with acute lung collapse who failed to re-expand with conventional methods were taken in the study. All the cases were subjected to complete history taking, clinical examination, chest X-ray, thoracic ultrasound followed by bronchoscopy.

Results: 36 patients who met the eligibility criteria were subjected to bronchoscopy. Malignancy was confirmed by endobronchial biopsy in 19 out of 36 cases. Infective etiology was confirmed in 12 cases. 5 cases out of the 36 did not show any significant etiology by bronchoscopy.

Conclusion: In cases with lung collapse, early bronchoscopic airway evaluation should be considered especially if the patients have known risk factors for malignancy.

Keywords: Bronchoscopy, Malignancy, Tuberculosis, Endobronchial Biopsy, BAL, Lung Collapse.

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Introduction

Flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy is an invasive procedure that is used for both diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. It has a high yield for diagnosing respiratory diseases [1]. It plays a significant role in diagnosing patients with infections, lung masses, and lung collapse [2]. It can also be used therapeutically in cases of foreign body aspiration, clearance of secretions causing airway collapse [3].

Lung collapse may be broadly attributed to obstructive or non-obstructive insults. Obstructive

collapse (mucous plugs, endobronchial lesions and foreign bodies) disrupts the alveolar-airway continuity, resulting in the resorption of trapped distal gas and subsequent atelectasis [4]. Non-obstructive collapse may be further characterized as extrapulmonary or intrapulmonary. Pleural diseases (i.e., pleural effusions or pneumothorax) and chest wall masses are extrapulmonary disorders that produce atelectasis via direct lung compression [5], whereas non-obstructive intrapulmonary atelectasis may result from surfactant deficiency or infiltrative parenchymal disease [6].

At present, there are no standard guidelines for the management of lung collapse, which is typically focused on addressing specific underlying conditions. In this study, we aim to use fiber optic bronchoscopy as a tool to diagnose and manage the conditions causing lung collapse.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective observational study was carried out in 36 patients admitted to the Government Hospital for Chest and Communicable Diseases, Visakhapatnam from October 2023 to March 2024 after obtaining approval from the ethical committee.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients suspected of having obstructive lung collapse due to endobronchial obstruction by a foreign body occluding the airway.
2. Patients with lung collapse due to extra-bronchial compression by tumor, lymph node, or pleural diseases (E.g. effusion or pneumothorax).
3. Patients with documented longstanding collapse.

Exclusion Criteria

1. HIV - Reactive cases.
2. Deranged coagulation profile.
3. Compromised cardiovascular status.
4. Patients with poor general condition.

Procedure

Patients presenting with acute lung collapse that failed to re-expand with conventional methods like chest physiotherapy or lung recruitment maneuvers were included. All the study subjects were subjected to Full history taking, clinical examination, chest X-ray before and after the procedure, thoracic ultrasound, arterial blood gas analysis, and CT chest. Bronchoscopy was done using a Fujin on flexible video bronchoscope. Endobronchial brushings, washings, and BAL were also obtained. Endobronchial lung biopsies were taken. The biopsy specimens were fixed in formalin and Haematoxylin-eosin-stained sections were examined. Special stains including Ziehl-Neelsen, and Periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) were done. Endobronchial washing and BAL were analysed for the total and differential count, microbiological examination, and cytological evaluation.

Results

A total of 36 patients met our inclusion criteria. Among 36 cases, 13 were females and 23 were

males. The mean age of the subjects was 45 years. Majority of the cases presented with cough with expectoration, chest pain, hemoptysis, breathlessness and fever. A few of the cases presented with loss of weight and loss of appetite. 19 patients were presented with acute onset of symptoms of less than 1 month. 13 patients were presented with symptoms of 1-2 months. 4 patients were presented with symptoms of more than 2 months. A suspicion of malignancy in 28 patients and infective etiology in the remaining 8 patients were clinically diagnosed. were excluded due to extrathoracic lung compression that resolved after drainage of pleural fluid. On radiological analysis, 19 patients had right-sided lung opacity, among whom 7 patients had opacity in the right upper lobe, 6 in the right middle lobe, and 6 in the right lower lobe. 17 patients had left-sided lung opacity among whom 8 patients had opacity in the upper lobe, 5 in the lower lobe and 4 in the lingular segment. Bronchoscopic findings revealed that 20 patients had endobronchial growth, 7 patients had bronchial stenosis, 5 patients had erythematous mucosa and 4 patients did not reveal any significant findings. Malignancy was diagnosed in 23 (63.8%) based on histopathological examination through biopsy and 13 had non-neoplastic causes.

Among the neoplastic cases, 12 cases were diagnosed as squamous cell carcinoma, 7 as adenocarcinoma, 3 as non-small cell carcinoma, and 1 as pulmonary synovial sarcoma. Among non-neoplastic cases, 7 were diagnosed as tuberculosis, 2 as pneumonia, and 2 as fungal infection. 2 cases were undiagnosed due to inadequate samples. Bronchial brushings, bronchial washing, biopsy was done for all 36 patients, among which bronchial washing was positive only in 14 patients with 56 % sensitivity, 74% specificity, 78.73% Positive predictive value, 34.56% of negative predictive value. Bronchial brushings were positive for 23 out of 36 patients with a sensitivity of 84.85%, specificity of 75%, positive predictive value of 85.86%, and negative predictive value of 73%. Bronchial biopsies were positive for 23 out of 36 patients with a sensitivity of 86%, specificity of 88%, positive predictive value of 95.34%, and negative predictive value of 74.38%. Among the non-neoplastic category, tuberculosis was diagnosed in 7 cases, pneumonia was diagnosed in 2 cases, and fungal infection was isolated in 2 cases. On fungal culture, 1 sample showed aspergillosis and 1 sample showed penicillium growth. 2 cases remained undiagnosed due to inadequate samples.

Table 1: Distribution of the lesions diagnosed using bronchoscopy

Aetiology	Fiberoptic bronchoscopy n=36
Endobronchial malignancy	23(63.8%)
Tuberculosis	7(19.4%)
Fungal infection	2(0.05%)
Pneumonia	2 (0.05%)
Inadequate sample	2(0.05%)

Table 2: Histotypes of endobronchial neoplastic lesions by bronchial biopsy

Tumor type	Stage	Patient total n=23
Squamous cell carcinoma n=12 (52.17%)	Stage III B	4
	Stage IV	8
Adenocarcinoma n=7 (30.4%)	Stage IA	1
	Stage IIIB	2
	Stage IV	4
Small cell carcinoma n= 3 (13%)	Extensive	3
Pulmonary synovial sarcoma n=1 (0.04%)	Stage IV	1

Table 3: Comparison between different techniques:

	Bronchial washing	Bronchial brushing	Bronchial Biopsy
Sensitivity	56 %	84.85%	86%
Specificity	74%	75%	88%
Positive predictive value	78.73%	85.68%	95.34%
Negative predictive value	34.56%	73 %	74.38%

Discussion

Bronchoscopy is a vital, well-established tool with rising attractiveness in respiratory medicine.⁷ Bronchoscopy must be properly indicated and performed in a safe and effective manner. It is an operator-dependent procedure and outcomes may vary according to different methods and techniques.^[8]

Collapse is an important sign of pulmonary disease. Therefore, it is necessary to use diagnostic tools such as fiberoptic bronchoscopy to get an accurate diagnosis of the underlying cause in a patient presenting with collapse on chest radiograph or CT-Chest. ^[9] The major causes of collapse of lung include Lung Cancer, Endobronchial tuberculosis, infection, endobronchial metastasis, bronchiectasis, foreign body, mucous plug. ^[10] The most common cause of lobar collapse is obstruction by a central endobronchial lesion.^[11]

In an adult with collapse, a centrally obstructing neoplasm should always be considered as the underlying cause.^[12] Suspected neoplasm was the most common indication for bronchoscopy. ^[13] Endoscopically visible endobronchial lesions have higher diagnostic yield as compared to peripheral lesions. ^[14] According to recent evidence, the expected diagnostic yield of combined endoscopically visible lesions and bronchial biopsy amounts to 90%. A minimum of five samples are required to achieve 90% diagnostic likelihood in biopsies of visible tumors. Peripheral lesions are

approached via combined bronchoscopic techniques, such as BAL, biopsy and fine needle aspiration. In these lesions, size and possibility of fluoroscopic visualization are the major determinants of diagnostic yield. Bronchogenic carcinoma is relatively uncommon in adults under the age of 40. Bronchial biopsies and bronchial brushings can be taken for pathological examination and a direct assessment can be made.

10–40% of patients with active pulmonary tuberculosis have endobronchial tuberculosis. 25–35% of endobronchial tuberculosis patients present as a collapse on chest radiograph. Therefore, bronchoscopy is a valuable tool in diagnosing endobronchial tuberculosis. One case each of penicillium and aspergillus infection were also diagnosed. Tuberculous granulomas were found in 7 cases (19.44%). In the suspected non-neoplastic group brushings and washings were not found useful.

Conclusion

Our study confirmed the important role of bronchoscopy in lung collapse. In those with lung collapse and risk factors for malignancy, early bronchoscopic airway evaluation should be considered to exclude obstructive neoplasms and to avoid diagnostic/therapeutic delays. Bronchial washing cultures are also warranted in some patients, who may harbor tubercular, fungal, or antibiotic-resistant organisms. Hence, fiberoptic bronchoscopy can be employed for the diagnosis of

patients presenting with collapse of lung/lobe on chest X-ray or CT-Chest lung diseases. However further studies are needed to evaluate the diagnostic and therapeutic role of bronchoscopy in lung collapse.

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